

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B208
Date: 10th June 2006
Take Off: 11:07:04
Landing: 16:26:48
Flight Time: 5h 20m

Campaign: CAPEX VPRACOP

Trials Instructions:

Operating Area: Beja area

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Dave Kindred	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
6	CVI	Jeff Brown	Met Office
7	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
8	Cloud Physics	Paul James	FAAM
9	SWS	Ian Rule	Met Office
10	CCN	Bruce Giddings	Met Office
11	Wet Neph / PSAP	James Bowles	Met Office
12	Filters 1	Doug Anderson	FAAM
13	VPRACOP 1/Radon	Fernando Carvalho	Instituto Tecnologie de Nulcear
14	VPRACOP 2/Filters 2	Joao Oliveira	Instituto Tecnologie de Nulcear
15	CLAPREC 1	Piotr Drzweicki	University of Warsaw
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track: B208 Track 10-JUN-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b208
 Date: 10 Jun 2006
 Project: CAPEX VPRACOP
 Location: Beja, Portugal

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
092343		Start-Up	0.00 kft	114	38'05.13N,7'55.65W
103142		INU	0.46 kft	114	Set to Navigate
110704		T/O	4.1 kft	170	Beja
111536	111701	Profile 1	7.0 - 6.0 kft	161	
111852	112521	Profile 1	6.0 - 1.9 kft	001	End 2k' on Q1018mb
112518		Video	2.0 kft	004	Start FFC & DFC
112521	114016	Run 1.1	1.9 kft	011	2k' on Q1018
114115		Event	1.9 kft	144	Change alt in turn
114223	115724	Run 1.2	1.9 kft	187	2k'
115724	120211	Profile 2	1.9 - 3.9 kft	187	2k' - 4k'
120350	122050	Run 2.1	3.9 kft	007	Extend N. to Evora
Evora					
122235	123734	Run 2.2	3.9 kft	178	Southbound
123735	123952	Profile 3	3.9 - 6.0 kft	175	1000fpm
124333	124746	Profile 3	6.0 - 10.0 kft	004	1000fpm
124746	130247	Run 3.1	10.0 kft	002	
125724		Video	10.0 kft	002	Change tapes
130431	131934	Run 3.2	10.0 kft	184	Southbound
131934	132437	Profile 4	10.0 - 15.0 kft	187	1000fpm
132629	134159	Run 4.1	15.0 kft	002	Northbound
134357	135858	Run 4.2	15.0 kft	182	Southbound
140056	141040	Profile 5	15.0 - 25.0 kft	004	1000fpm , North
141040	142543	Run 5.1	25.0 kft	000	Northbound
142747	144247	Run 5.2	25.0 kft	185	Southbound
143034		Video	25.0 kft	185	Change tapes
144454	145518	Profile 6	25.1 - 32.3 kft	353	1000fpm to FL270
145526	150020	Profile 6	32.3 - 34.0 kft	357	400fpm
150020	150750	Run 6.1	34.0 kft	342	Across sun
150917	151647	Run 6.2	34.1 - 34.0 kft	256	Into Sun
151811	152541	Run 6.3	34.1 - 34.0 kft	166	Across Sun
152702	153432	Run 6.4	34.1 - 34.0 kft	084	Down Sun
153939	154229	Orbit 1	34.1 - 33.9 kft	294	35deg left from 300deg
154325	154703	Orbit 2	34.1 - 33.9 kft	261	30deg left,from 260
154839	160825	Profile 7	34.1 - 10.0 kft	204	1000fpm
160510		Video	13.9 kft	176	End Tapes
160654		Event	10.5 kft	176	Abeam Evora
161009	161233	Profile 7	10.1 - 8.0 kft	357	1000fpm
161444	161656	Profile 7	8.0 - 6.0 kft	174	1000fpm
162648		Land	0.54 kft	178	Beja 162648
163114		Shutdown	0.53 kft	104	38'05.13N, 7'55.65W

B208 Track 10-JUN-06

SORTIE BRIEF

B208: 10/06/06

VPRACOP (Dedicated sortie)

Programme: EUFAR (European Fleet for Airborne Research)

Project: CAPEX (Clouds and Aerosol over Portugal Experiment)

May/June 2006

Conditions/Weather:

Clear or partly cloudy conditions. The main objective is to remain clear of cloud whilst sampling at various vertical levels.

Trial Objectives:

- To measure the vertical distribution of radon in a vertical stack over land.
- To measure aerosol particles/expose filters in differing vertical layers from natural & anthropogenic sources.

Location:

Central/S. Portugal, over land, likely in Beja area (over land, in LPR 51).

Flight Pattern:

1. Depart Beja and climb to 5000 ft to prepare for first run. (10 min).
2. Profile descent into selected area, at 1000 ft/min, to lowest permitted altitude. (5 min).
3. Set up racetrack pattern at 500ft within selected area, of reciprocal 15 min S&L legs, giving a time call at 10 minute intervals for filter sampling. (35 min).
4. Profile ascent to next selected level (1500 ft) at 500 ft/min. (5 min).
5. Repeat 3 at 1500 ft, then profile ascend to 5000 ft at 500 ft/min. (45 min).
6. Repeat 3 at 5000 ft, then ascend to FL100 at 1000 ft/min. (40 min).
7. Repeat 3 at FL 100, then ascend to FL150 at 1000 ft/min. (40 min).
8. Repeat 3 at FL 150, then ascend to FL 250 at 1000 ft/min. (45 min).
9. Repeat 3 at FL 250, then ascend to FL350, at 1000 ft/min if possible. (45 min).
10. Recover to Beja. (20 min).

[Total time : 5 hr 00 mins]

Note: If cloud exists at any selected level, climb or descend to nearest level above/below this to remain clear of cloud, as defined by Mission Scientist.

DRK

09/06/06

Mission Scientist Debriefing Sheet

Flight No. B208 VPRACOP (Dedicated flight).

Date: 10/06/2006 (Vertical distribution of aerosols & Radon).

Assessment of the Flight:

Overall, a successful flight achieving the aims of the sortie (to measure the vertical distribution of radon, and to expose filters to measure aerosol particles from natural and anthropogenic sources, in differing layers, in a vertical stack over land).

The flight went very much as planned, but with extra SWS/SHIMS/BBR runs & orbits at max altitude, and an extra deep profile heading back from the N of Beja towards base at the end of the flight. Weather conditions – see below - were good (little cloud, good visibility, light winds in the BL and a main top to the Aerosol pollution at about 8,200 ft). Instrumentation worked well, apart from some NO_x box measured values – to be investigated post flight; CVI problems in the filter sampling mode; and some of the exposed filters by the VPRACOP group being damaged during mounting, exposure and dismounting. CCN provided some good samples, especially at lower levels in pollution.

After T/O from Beja at 1107z, we climbed to FL 070 locally, then profiled down at 1000 ft/min to 2000 ft (constant pressure alt), before commencing:

1. Runs 1.1/1.2: a reciprocal racetrack pattern, at 2000 ft AMSL, with long 15-minute legs orientated S-N, then N-S, turning at the N end, and passing to E of Evora (about 17 nm on N'ward leg, and about 22 nm on Southbound leg). The run was only about 500 ft AGL (local altimeter setting 1018 mb) as we turned onto reciprocal at N end. This was followed by a profile climb, P2, at 500 ft/min, from 2000 ft to 4000 ft (to stay at level underneath shallow Cu cloud).
2. Runs 2.1/2.2: a reciprocal racetrack pattern, at 4000 ft AMSL, with long 15-minute legs orientated S-N, then N-S, turning at the N end almost due E of Evora, with nearest approach at about 9.7 nm from LIDAR site as we began Run 2.2. We were abeam Beja on Northbound run at about 8nm. This was followed by a profile climb, P3, at 1000 ft/min, from 4000 ft to FL 100.
3. Runs 3.1/3.2: a reciprocal racetrack pattern, at FL100, with long 15-minute legs orientated S-N, then N-S, turning at the N end. This was followed by a profile climb, P4, at 1000 ft/min, from FL100 to FL 150.
4. Runs 4.1/4.2: a reciprocal racetrack pattern, at FL150, with long 15-minute legs orientated S-N, then N-S, turning at the N end. This was followed by a turn onto N, then profile climb, P5, at 1000 ft/min, from FL150 to FL 250.
5. Runs 5.1/5.2: a reciprocal racetrack pattern, but centred further to N, at FL250, with long 15-minute legs orientated S-N, then N-S, turning at the N end. This was followed by a turn onto N, then profile climb, P6, at 1000 ft/min initially, but slowly reducing to 400 ft/min towards end of climb due to a/c performance, from FL 250 to FL 340.

6. Runs for VPRACOP at FL 340 were organised into a Box pattern, 7.5 mins per leg, proceeding anticlockwise from legs cross sun (Run 6.1), into sun (R6.2), cross sun (R6.3), and finally down sun (R6.4), keeping clear of Ci cloud as far as possible.
7. We then transited a little further N. to be clear of almost all Ci cloud (a small amount remained to S), then performed 2 x orbits at max bank at that altitude - 35 deg bank for Orbit 1, then 30 deg bank for Orbit 2, anticlockwise, also for SWS/SHIMS.
8. After re-positioning, we finally performed a deep profile descent (P7) from FL 340 to FL060 at 1000 ft/min, being abeam Evora at 161050z, at about 9,500 ft.
9. After completing P7 at 161656, at FL 060, and re-positioning, we made a short transit to Beja, landing at 1627z.

Summary of weather conditions:

Slack surface pressure gradient over Portugal. Low pressure to W of Iberia, anticyclone to E & SE of UK.

Winds L&V up to about 10,000 ft, mainly W'yly above with speeds increasing to about 50 kt at FL340 during box pattern.

Cloud: shallow cumulus, base about 4000 ft initially, tops (under inversion) at about 5200 ft, but dissipating as Boundary Layer depth gradually rose through the day. Some (generally 1-2/8, max 4/8) residual shallow Cu left, mainly to West and North west of operating area. Cirrus, base well above FL340, generally thinned and reduced in amount during the sortie. The main pollution/aerosol layer top was just over 8000ft (visually, being clear above; and confirmed by tephigram plot, and PCASP aerosol readings). A small gap between pollution layers was present early in the flight at 5100 ft to 5400 ft.

DRK.

11/06/06

Mission Scientist's Log

VPPA COP (Dedicated Sortie).

PAID DISTRIBUTION
AEROSOL PARTICLES

Flight No **B.208**

Date **10/06/06**

Page **1** of **7**

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					QNH = 1018 mb $T_{temp} = 21^{\circ}C$ $T_{PT} = 15^{\circ}C$
1059					START TRACK at Beja 1/8 Cu (shallow) $Tops \sim 500'$ Base $\sim 3000-3500$ 6/8 thin Ci above Wind $300^{\circ}/06$ kt.
1107			\rightarrow		T/O Beja. Climb initially to Flt 70. Bl. hazy/polluted.
				2-3/8 Mainly L West	C. Base 4000 - 4200' [Cu Base] C. Tops 5200' [Cu Tops]
1114	Above	most of			Pollution layer here 7/8 thin Ci above.
111536	START P1	Flt 70	163	37 ³⁰ N 7 ³⁶ W	START P1 Flt 70 \downarrow 1000' / mi Wind $285^{\circ}/5$ kts.
111701	Interrupt P1				Interrupt P1 at Flt 60 Turn \downarrow
111852	START P1	Flt 60	007	37 ³⁰ N 7 ⁴² W	Descend \downarrow 1000' / mi to 2000' Clear of Cu here in S (SSE of Beja) Line of convection ahead
112100					Passing 4700' (inversion/hydrolyse here) Counts 100 \rightarrow 600 PCASP (C. Physics) as descent now visibility INTO AEROSOL/POLLUTION LAYER HERE.
					Some problems with CVI.
112330		3000'	\rightarrow 005		Most Cu to W now. (v. little to R) (only Cu ahead)
112528	END P1 START R1.1	1.814 ft 2000 FT.	007	37 ³² N 7 ³⁶ W	End P1 / Start R1.1.
112720			\rightarrow		Abeam Beja (Sibs) [to W. of us]
113500					1-2/8 Cu here. 1/8 Ci thinner here, but contrails.
113600			\rightarrow		Abeam ENDA (~ 17 nm to W)
					CVI has leak in filter system?
113645			\rightarrow	Ridge	Hills to port now (highest along whole of run)
114016	END R1.1	1.814 ft		36 ⁴² N 07 ¹⁸ W	End R1.1. Turn \downarrow at end of racetrack

(Need to climb few hundred feet to avoid terrain during turn)

[500' AGL at end of run - staying at 2000' ASL]

Mission Scientist's Log

SPICOM: \nearrow Ci
 Low Conv
 Ci virtually gone
 Inv/4/d.r.
 Top of poll. layer

Flight No **B.208**.....

Date **10/06/06**.....

Page **2** of **7**

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
114223	START R1.2	1.8 kft 2000 ft.	169°	38°36'N 7°24'W	Start R1.2, heading S. on 2nd part of Race-track. 1.1. Wind Lev. (< 3m/sec) \searrow 2 1.2
114720			\rightarrow		EVERA \rightarrow NM Abaan (to SHed). CVI ^{will work} in Aerosol mode only for rest of flight. (Problems with Filters mode)
115238				\Rightarrow	Little ⁽⁺⁾ Cu left in this area. Base has lifted to near/at inversion. STILL 6/8-7/8 Ci (some thicker patches)
115530			\leftarrow		4 TH Sample now on CW
115724	R1.2 / P2	1.8 kft (2000 ft)	190°	37°45'N 7°30'W	End R1.2 / START P2 at 800/mi [1018] [QNH] Climb to 4000' for next level (to stay under any remaining Cu cloud).
120211	END P2	3.8 kft (4000 ft)	269°	37°24'N 7°36'W	End P2 at 4000'. Turn \rightarrow onto reciprocal.
120350	START R2.1	3.8 kft (4000 ft)	001°		Start R2.1 at 4000' (Heading N). Pollution layer / Aerosol top appear to be above or N 5000 ft.
120845			\rightarrow		PCASP (C. Physics) ~ 600 counts & steady along run. CVI not working now in Aerosol mode. Trace Cu ahead (almost down to NW now)
121330			\rightarrow		Abaan Beja airfield (8 miles to Port) Will pass closer to Evera at N. end of Race-track (slightly further W on this Race-track).
121500	END R2.1	3.8 kft 4000 ft	001°	38°36'N 7°36'W	End R2.1 at 4000' (Hdg N) 17 min Turn \rightarrow towards EVERA at this height.
122235	START R2.2	3.8 kft 4000 ft	179°	38°30'N 7°36'W	Start R2.2 (heading) 9.7 nm to EVERA (to W).

Mission Scientist's Log

8ave Flight Comm 1100
1600

Flight No **B.208**

Date **10/06/06**

Page **3** of **7**

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
122930	R 2-2	3.8kft	176°	35° 6' N 7° 36' W	WIND 320/4-5 m/sec.
123330			←		CCW Samples working well at this level.
123735	END R2-2	3.8kft 4000ft	176°	37° 36' N 7° 36' W	End R2-2 / Start P3 400' / FL060 (at 1000/m)
123806					Changing to 1013 mb.
					Continue along this track up to FL060. CLEAN PHYSICS PCASP now counts at 5200/. ✓
123952	Intercept P3	FL060			Intercept P3 at FL060 Turn into reciprocal
124005			→		PCASP counts rising again. Then continue climb to FL100. Another Pollution haze layer above.
124333	Resume P3	FL060			Resume P3 at 1000'
					PCASP dropped from 600 → virtually nil. ⇒ 8200 FT. (Pollution layer up to this height secondary).
124746	END P3 Start R3-1	FL100 (10.0kft)	002°	37° 54' N 7° 36' W	End P3 / Start R3-1 (Heading N).
130247	END R3-1	FL100	002°		End R3-1 (N'bd) Turn into reciprocal.
130431	XMIT R3-2				Start R3-2 (S'bd)
130800	R 3-2	10.0kft	185°	38° 36' N 7° 30' W	→ WIND 325/6 m/sec. Pollution/haze layers below. Sol Cu to West 7/8 Ci (some thin/some thick) + contrails above. PCASP (Clean Physics) concurs, no general at this height.
131730					CVI now plumbed in as originally set up for sortie; working better.
131934	END R3-2 Start PA	10.0kft	187°	37° 44' N 7° 30' W	End R3-2 / FL100 / FL150 1000' / min. Start PA (Continue on this track up to FL150)
132437	END PA	15.0kft	186°	37° 24' N 7° 36' W	End PA at FL150 & Turn into reciprocal
					[Temp -3°C. DP -6°C WIND 290/7-8 m/sec]

Mission Scientist's Log

WFO/Anderson
Orbits

ideal

Flight No **B 208**.....

Date 10/06/06.....

Page 4 of 7

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
132629	START R4.1	15.0kft	360°	37°30'N 7°36'W	Start W'nd Run 4.1 Photo 1 of circular water/field area (To Port) Abeam. (Light green colour) 250/7msec ⁻¹ W/ly/20kts [Horiz Wind] [Flight Deck Wind]
134159	END R4.1	15.0kft	360°	38°42'N 7°36'W	END R4.1 (Evolve ahead to W) turn S (Ozwl Cu, shallen to E) 1/8 flat cumulus to west (along line). Otherwise 6/8 Ci above (THINNING?).
134357	START R4.2	15.0kft	184°	38°30'N 7°36'W	Start R4.2, S'ly. WIND 270/9m/sec. [Temp = -3.1°C; DPT = -11.7°C]
1353	→				Photo 2/3 looking PORT/STBD at ↓ Ci above general pollution below + Cu line in distance (to E) ↓ Ci above, - " - (Cu line to W)
135858	END R4.2	15.0kft	185°	37°30'N 7°36'W	End R4.2, turn ↓ onto N, then climb to FL250.
140056	START PS	15.0kft	357°	37°36'N 7°36'W	Start PS FL250 → FL250 at 1000'/min.
141040	END PS START R5.1	25.0kft	360°	36°18'N 7°36'W	End PS at FL250, & start R5.1. 1/8 Cu to NW & to NE (less) shallen well to NW. 1/8 Ci above (contrails)
1413	→				Pragly Evom (to Port) Will travel further N. of this race track.
1419					Wind 285°/14msec ⁻¹ . IA Temp -24°C; DPT -33.7°C
142543	END R5.1	25.0kft	354°	39°36'N 7°24'W	End R5.1; Turn ↷ onto Reciprocal (opposite direction) on this run
142747	START R5.2	24.91kft	191°		Start R5.2, southward.
144247	END R5.2	25.0kft	186°	35°12'N 7°36'W	End R5.2. Turn ↷ & climb to FL340 afterwards

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.208**

Date **30/06/06**

Page **5** of **7**

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
144454	START P6	25.0kft	358°	36°18'N 7°42'W	Start P6 FL250 → FL340 at 400'/min 5/8 Ci ahead (to N) Contrails ahead also
1450					Climb rate now ~500'/min (gradually lessening with A/C performance)
145315			→		Cloud 6/8 Ci (mainly thin, some contrails) 2/8 Cu to West & North, (Mod (shallow) otherwise clear of cloud)
1455					↑ rate of climb now 400'/min
145925					Contrails & Ci still above (but thinning)
					Will work box pattern ↙ ↘ ↙ ↘ at FL 340° ① ↙ ② ↘ ③ ↙ ④ ↘ (but no CBTS)
150020	END P6 START R6.1	34.0kft	341°	39°48'N 7°36'W	FL 340 now, end P6, start R6.1 [class sub] (N of Evara/Bogja area) Clear of Ci ahead (above)
150750	END R6.1	34.0kft	344°	40°30'N 7°42'W	END R6.1. *CLEAR OF CI IN THIS AREA NOW * More significant convection to NW development
1					Ice forming on filter, supply pipe (IAT -49°C)
150917	START R6.2	34.0kft	255°	40°30'N 7°54'W	START R6.2 [into sub]
1515					Ci clear at this level (& above) Partly Ci, Cu shallower below, larger Cu out to NORTH
151647	END R6.2	34.0kft	255°	40°18'N 8°42'W	END R6.2; turn into X sun track heading SSE (Sun to SWS)
151811	START R6.3	34.0kft	266°	40°12'N 8°42'W	START R6.3 WIND 235 / 26 m/sec (Hodaxe) IATemp = -49.3°C IAT = -50.0°C (electr) 242 / 25 m/sec
					Some Ci well ahead, clear above & to ESW

Az 252°

Az 253°

Az 252°
255°

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B 208**.....

 Date **30/06/06**.....

 Page **6** of **7**.....

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
152541	END R6.3	34.0kft	166	39°30'N 8°12'W	End R6.3 Turning
152702	START R6.4	34.0kft	082°	39°30'N 8°6'W	Start R6.4, Downson (Save Ci to S) winds 250°/16 m/sec. Will come under v. thin Ci soon, At end of this run, will head N for 2-3 mins to clear of this Ci before 2x Orbits, 30°, clockwise
152930					Coming under thin Ci now
153432	END R6.4	34.0kft	082°	39°42'N 7°86'W	At end of this run, will head N to clear Ci before doing 2 orbits End R6.4 [A/c controlling at FL360 above, still below Ci above]
153800					Clearing Ci behind us now
153939	START ORB 1.	34.0kft		40°06'N 7°15'W	Start Orbit 1 for SWs/SWMS [35° L of bank] Wind 226/15 m/sec
154229	END ORB 1	34.0kft	250°		End Orbit 1 Visually clear of Ci (<30° to S) (v. thin Ci above) (from Pit Manager)
154325	START ORB 2.	34.0kft	260°	40°06'N 7°18'W	Start Orbit 2 AT 30° BANK [230°/18 m/sec]
154703	END ORB 2.	"	Passing 250°		End Orbit 2 Continue to 205° + Await clearance for profile descent from FL340
154839	START P7	34.0kft	203°	39°54'N 7°18'W	Start P7, 1000'/min ↓ towards BEJA
155701					Passing FL200
160442	P7.	14.1kft	177°	38°42'N 7°42'W	Descent continuing
160630					Passed Evora to 8thd.
160825	P7	10.0kft	177°	38°30'N 7°36'W	Interrupt P7 at FL100, turn S

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG FOR FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight Number : B208

Date : 10/06/06

Operator and contact info : Kate Turnbull katet@faam.ac.uk

Problems with Instruments

CO	Background ppbV became very high above FL150, resulting in unreliable data, especially during profile descent after calibration at FL340.
O₃	None
NO_x	No flow through Ozonator at FL100 and above therefore only NO channel available (no NO₂ or NO_x measurements)
SO₂	N/A
TDLAS	N/A
WAS	N/A

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B208

Date: 10/6/06	Operator: papj	DRS Time: 07:35:00	DAU1 Time: +1	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: 0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 1
---------------	----------------	--------------------	---------------	---------------	--------------	---------------	---------------	-------------

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
111539	200	0.08		10	5											Start p1 070	
111656	350	0.08		10	5											060	
112025	70	0.09		10	5											050	
112150	700	0.09		10	5											040	
112345	700	0.09		10	5											030	
112520	700	0.09		10	5											020 end p1 start 1.1	
1126	700	0.09		10	5												
1129	700	0.09		10	5												
1131	700	0.09		10	12 mw												
1134	700	0.09		10	9.5Kv												
1137	700	0.09		10	5												
1140	900	0.09		10	5												
114016	900	0.09		10	5											End run 1.1	
114233	900	0.09		10	5											Start run 1.2	
1145	900	0.09		10	5												
1149	800	0.09		10	5												
1153	700	0.09		10	5												
1157	700	0.09		10	5												
115724				10	5											End run 1.2	
120012	650	0.09		10	5											030	
120211				10	5											End p2	
120350	600	0.09		10	5											Start 2.1	
1205	600	0.09		10	5												
1209	600	0.09		10	5												
1213	600	0.09		10	5												
1217	600	0.09		10	5												
122050				10	5											End 2.1	
122235	600	0.09														Start run 2.2	
1225	600	0.09															
1229	700	0.09															
1234	500	0.09															
123735	600	0.09														End run 2.2	
1240	600	0.08														060	
124530	50	0.08														080	
124746	40	0.09														Run 3.1	
1251	25	0.09															
1255	10	0.09															
1259	15	0.1															
1304	10	0.09															
130247																End run 3.1	
130431	10	0.09														Start 3.2	
1308	10	0.09															
131934	10	0.08														End 3.2	
132350	30	0.08														140	
132629	10	0.09														Start run 4.1	

CCN LOG

T₆

ALLEVIATOR GMT		HEIGHT ± T _c	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS
ON	OFF	2000'		1 1.75	2 2.5	3 3.5	4 4.25	5 5.5	
112528	112605	23.95	21.8	0.18	0.32	0.50	0.71	1.08	S Run 1.1
		23.93	20.93	331	412	789	755	1420	D
		24.05	20.9	255	248	246	244	280	B
		24.02	19.59	2417	2411	2387	2375	2398	R
		23.77	18.48	996.8	996.6	996.8	996.6	996.6	P
		2000'							
113558	113640	24.09	21.85	0.17	0.32	0.50	0.78	1.0	S Run 1.1
		24.13	21.14	272	513	673	613	1482	D
		24.16	20.39	246	245	246	251	26	B ↓ Turn onto
			19.44	2344	2338	2331	2328	2335	R Run 1.2
Run + 30 sec			18.69	996.5	996.4	996.6	996.5	996.5	P
		2000'		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
114410	114552	24.31	22.05	0.18	0.31	0.49	0.72	1.08	S Run 1.2
		24.32	21.32	249	513	653	1045	926	D
		24.32	20.6	237	251	245	255	286	B
		24.31	19.81	2322	2320	2325	2329	2334	R
		24.31	18.77	996.5	996.5	996.5	996.6	996.6	P
		2000'							
115205	115255	24.40	22.14	0.17	0.32	0.49	0.71	1.08	S Run 1.2
		24.45	21.4	258	637	597	1123	1374	D
		24.46	20.73	241	242	250	254	284	B e.o. run
		24.43	19.28	2364	2380	2382	2376	2372	R
		24.41	18.95	996.6	996.5	996.6	996.5	996.6	P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	

108

FLIGHT NUMBER: B	DATE: 10/06/06	OPERATOR: BROUCE GIDDINGS	Page 1 of 2
PROJECT: CAPEX			

CCN LOG

T6

ALLEVIATOR GMT		HEIGHT & TC	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS
ON	OFF			1	2	3	4	5	
		4000'		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
120350	120433	24.72	22.50	0.17	0.31	0.49	0.71	1.07	S Run 2-1
		26.90	21.86	226	532	515	984	1355	D
		24.83	21.13	238	252	250	264	279	B
		24.79	21.97	2414	244	2413	2416	2427	R
12		24.76	21.77	296.6	296.6	296.6	296.5	296.5	P
		4000'							
121315	121355	24.84	22.8	0.17	0.31	0.49	0.71	1.06	S 2-1
		24.97	21.92	293	357	433	1058	1189	D
		24.92	21.14	248	249	257	272	284	B e.o.f. 24
		24.92	20.4	2433	2437	2445	2448	2443	R
SOR	2-2	24.92	19.44	296.8	296.6	296.8	296.8	296.8	P sor 2-2
		4000'		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
122350	122432	25.04	22.80	0.17	0.31	0.49	0.71	1.06	S 2-2
		25.04	21.90	343	497	668	1030	1501	D
		24.94	21.20	267	269	272	279	285	B
		24.90	20.48	2449	2448	2445	2447	2446	R
123015		24.75	19.50	296.6	296.6	296.6	296.6	296.6	P ref.
		4000'							
123225	123310	25.14	22.88	0.17	0.31	0.49			S 2-2
		25.15	22.12	315	448	727			D
		25.13	21.28	273	278	277			B
				2438	2438	2439			R
				296.6	296.5	293.3			P Prof 30 3
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	

208

FLIGHT NUMBER: B	DATE: 10/06/06	OPERATOR: B-GIROING	Page 1 of 2
PROJECT:			

CCN LOG

ALLEVIATOR GMT		HEIGHT #76	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS	
ON	OFF	10000'		1	2	3	4	5		
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
		25-20	23-08	0.17	0.31	0.49	0.72	1.08	S	Run 3-1
		25-26	22-19	175	193	316	552	660	D	
		25-19	21-40	234	235	258	252	250	B	
		25-06	20-53	242	243	242	2419	2419	R	
		25-05	19-43	976.6	976.9	976.7	976.9	976.8	P	20000051
		10000'								
130130	130200	24.96	22-72	0.17	0.31	0.49	0.71	1.07	S	Run 3-1
		24.99	22-01	178	275	328	320	529	D	(before 1st sample analysis)
		24.99	21-13	246	249	241	241	239	B	3.2 @ 2
		24.97	20-37	2410	2407	2404	2398	2394	R	
1311	45	24.85	19.27	976.7	976.6	976.7	976.8	976.7	P	
		10000'		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
131235	131320	24.76	22-53	0.17	0.31	0.49			S	Run 3-2
		24.68	21-68	161	200	288			D	end
		24.74	21-02	230	229	224			B	middle of 3
				2385	2383	2387			R	start of
				976.8	976.8	971.4			P	climb
									S	
									D	
									B	
									R	
									P	
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		

208

FLIGHT NUMBER: B	DATE: 10/06/06	OPERATOR: B. GIDDINGS	Page 1 of 2
PROJECT:			

CCN LOG

T6

ALLEVIATOR GMT		HEIGHT ± T6	TEMP INLET	STATIC						REMARKS
ON	OFF	15000'		1 1.75	2 2.5	3 3.5	4 4.25	5 5.5		
13:26:29	13:27:13	24.85	22.60	0.18	0.31	0.49	0.72	1.08	S	Run 4-1
		24.85	21.83	167	213	265	290	371	D	
		24.84	21.01	230	234	234	231	227	B	
		24.72	20.26	2388	2387	2396	2401	2405	R	
13:30:40		24.67	19.15	943.0	943.1	942.9	943.0	942.9	P	
		15000'								
13:39:03		24.63	22.40	0.17	0.31	0.49	0.71	1.08	S	cor by 1st analysis
13:40:38	13:41:20	24.66	21.57	162	160	224	162	356	D	
		24.55	20.87	228	228	231	225	226	B	
		24.40	19.96	2409	2411	2409	2409	2413	R	
13:52:20		24.31	18.87	943.1	943.1	943.0	943.0	942.9	P	
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
13:54:52	13:55:20	24.45	22.13	0.17	0.31	0.49			S	
		24.50	21.52	162	164	168			D	
		24.50	20.75	232	240	240			B	cor 2 (3)
				2395	2395	2392			R	SOP 5
				942.9	943.1	943.0			P	
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	S	
									D	
									B	
									R	
									P	
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		

208

FLIGHT NUMBER: B	DATE: 10/06/06	OPERATOR: B. G. 1001 NCS	Page 1 of 2
PROJECT: CAPEX			

CCN LOG

56

ALLEVIATOR GMT		HEIGHT + TC	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS
ON	OFF	25000'		1	2	3	4	5	
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
141040	141124	24.82	22.35 21.68	0.18	0.32	0.49	0.71 0.80	1.09	S Rev 5-1
		24.49	21.38 20.67	179	154	186	237	193	D
		24.52	20.78	235	255	240	244	251	B
		23.99	19.76	2344	2350	2355	2359	2359	R
142330		24.23	18.7	855.0	855.0	855.0	855.1	854.9	P
		25000'							
142530	142640	24.45	22.37	0.17	0.31	0.49	0.71	1.09	S 5-2
		24.49	21.22	196	147	184	206	140	D
		24.42	20.50	241	258	255	256	256	B
		24.32	19.78	2370	2374	2381	2392	2385	R
143740		24.31	18.15	855.0	854.9	855.0	855.0	855.1	P
		34000'		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
150610	150840	24.78	22.41	0.18	0.31	0.49	0.72	1.08	S Intake dirty Run 6-1
		24.79	20.64	240	182	184	184	179	D ear 62
		24.36	20.06	259	233	234	234	234	B ear 2
		23.75	19.75	242	2436	2446	2459	2467	R ear 2 (5)
		23.68	18.8	759.9	759.3	759.4	759.7	759.1	P
		34000'							
152702	152800	24.62	22.50	0.17	0.31	0.49	0.71	1.08	S R 6-4
		24.75	21.00	538	183	182	179	171	D
		24.47	20.36	250	273	267	261	258	B ear 2 ear 3
		24.58	19.8	2492	2497	2500	2503	2502	R
		24.52	18.43	759.2	759.4	759.8	759.8	759.5	P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B208

Date:

10 Jun 2006

Operator:

Joao / Doug

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet	90mm diameter type AC	Bottom inlet	90mm diameter type AC
-----------------------------------	-----------	-----------------------	--------------	-----------------------

Run No	Disk #1 TOP	Disk #2 MIDDLE	Disk #3 BOTTOM	Inlet Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
Filters run 1	AC42	-	-	Top	11:25:26	11:57:24	R1.1/2	2706	FL020 Filter pump started a few seconds after start of run. There was a brief increase in altitude of 200' at start of R1.2 End R1.1 flows: top: 1352, bottom : 2090 Start R1.2 flows: top: 1499, bottom: 2439
Filters run 1	AC43	-	-	Bottom	11:25:26	11:57:24	R1.1/2	4654	
Filters run 2	AC44	-	-	Top	12:03:50	12:37:	R2.1/2	3216	FL040 End R2.1 flows: top: 1699, bottom : 1180 Start R2.2 flows: top: 1860, bottom: 1266
Filters run 2	AC45	-	-	Bottom	12:03:50	12:37:	R2.1/2	2145	
Filters run 3	AC46	-	-	Top	12:47:46	13:19:34	R3.1/2	1893	FL100 Broken filter right round ring. Parts of filter lost during extraction from mount
Filters run 3	AC47	-	-	Bottom	12:47:46	13:19:34	R3.1/2	3466	FL100 Flows @ end of R3.1 top: 1746; Bottom: 943. @ start R3.2 top: 1924; Bottom: 1039
Filters run 4	AC48	-	-	Top	13:26:29	13:58:58	R4.1/2	2262	FL150 Both filters broken. AC49 fell on cabin floor while being removed from filter holder. End R4.1 flows: top: 1076, bottom : 1048 Start R4.2 flows: top: 1219, bottom: 1189
Filters run 4	AC49	-	-	Bottom	13:26:29	13:58:58	R4.1/2	2192	
Filters run 5	AC50	-	-	Top	14:10:40	14:42:47	R5.1/2	1667	FL250 Flows @ start of R5.2 top: 882; Bottom: 1047 AC50 broken, AC51 OK
Filters run 5	AC51	-	-	Bottom	14:10:40	14:42:47	R5.1/2	1984	
Filters run 6	AC52	-	-	Top	15:00:20	15:34:32	R6.1/2/3/4	424	FL340
Filters run 6	AC53	-	-	Bottom	15:00:20	15:34:32	R6.1/2/3/4	1027	FL340
Filters run 7	AC54	-	-	Top	15:48:39	16:16:56	P7	1087	FL340 down to FL060. Filter split
Filters run 7	AC55	-	-	Bottom	15:48:39	16:16:56	P7	3278	FL340 down to FL060
Ground	AC56	-	-	Top	17:37	18:04	Ground	2200	
Ground	AC57	-	-	Bottom	17:37	18:04	Ground	2038	

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.208**.....

 Date 10/6/06.....

 Operator's name: S.B......

 Page 1.... of 3....

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
11:19	P1	↓ 2000ft	1.2			↑ 35	18	
11:26		"				↓ 15.1		START OF P1 - CRAP START RH TO LOW
11:29		"		54	55	↑ 39	22	
11:35		"		53	72	↑ 40.5		
11:37		"		53	70	↑ 42.		
11:40		"		52	84	↑ 45	42	≈ 40% TYPICAL
11:43		"		52	87	↓ 15	45	- MAX RH! RECORDED
11:51		"		54	54	↑ 32		- A.T. MUST BE TOO WARM TO GET WITH RH.
11:54		"		51	66	↑ 39		
11:55		"		.	73	↑ 45		- 2 min to go Push for MAX RH
12:03		4000ft		44	88		45	START OF RUN
12:06		"		46	88	↓ 12		
12:14		"		45	54	↑ 27		RH STILL DROPPING BUT ZERO GROWTH SO ↓
12:17		"		45	59	↑ 45		EOR SLOW.
12:23				40	85		45	START OF RUN
12:24		"		42	85	↓ 12	45	TYPICAL GROWTH ≈ 40-50%
12:31		"		43	51	↑ 32		
12:34		"		41	61	↑ 38		
12:35		"		43	70.5	↑ 45	37	
12:37:35	P3			41	82	-	45	EOR 2.2 START OF P.3

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B208**.....

 Date **10/16/06**.....

 Operator's name: **SJS**.....

 Page **2** of **3**...

GMT	Run	Height ft	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
12:47:46	3.01	10,000ft	13.7	23	34.6		45	S.O.R.
12:51	"	"	13.9	24	32%	↓11	45	} JUST NOISE - SMALL SIGNALS.
12:59	"	"	13.9	24	48%	↑35	20	
13:02	"	"	13.7	25	61%	↑45		
13:04:31	3.2	"	13.8	25	80%		45	
13:09	"	"		25	78%	↓10	45	
13:17	"	"	13.9	24	39%	↑45		
13:19:34	P4	"	13.8	24	56%	-		EOR START OF P4 > 15,000
13:24:37	P4	15000	13.5	13.5	72%	↓42		EOP.
13:29	R4.1	"	13.6	11.9	65%	↓10		NOISE
13:37	"	"		7%	36%	↑30		NOISE
13:41	"	"		6%	47%	↑40		"
13:43:57	4.2	"	"	9%	63%	-		S.O.R 4.2
13:53	"	"	"	7	80%	↑45		WILL LEAVE HERE FOR EOR + PROFILE - NO AEROSOL - NOISE
14:02	P5							PROFILING ↑
14:10:47	R5.1	25,000	13.8	0%	31%		45	
14:15	"	"	"	"	30%	↓10		
14:25:43	EOP R5.1	"	"	"	23%	↑45		NOISE
14:27:47	R5.2	"	"	0%	55%	-		START OF RUN
14:32	"	"	"	"	72%	↓10		

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B 208** Date: 10th June 2006

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	Y	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	Y
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	Y
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	N
J. Williams	Y		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	N	Racks:	
FWVS	N	INC	N
<u>Radiometers</u>		CCN / CPC	Y
Upper Clear	Y	CVI (incl PCASP)	Y
“ Red	Y		
“ Silicon	Y		
“ SHIMS	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	Y
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	Y
		AMS	N
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
IR Camera	N		
TAFTS	N	<u>Others:</u>	
MARSS	N	AVAPS	N
DEIMOS	N	IR Camera	N
ARIES	N	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	Y	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	N
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	N	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	N
CO	Y	CPI	N
ORAC	N	Noxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B208

Date: 10th June 2006

Instruments

1. Printer – Not printing colours. Colour cartridge found to be wet with ink and also missing it's contact strip. Replaced cartridge and printed some test pages, still no colour.
2. HORACE Flight Summary – keeps entries made from previous day (i.e. with the same flight number).
3. Flight Manager's display locked up in flight, rebooted pc then okay.
4. CVI problem after t/o, possible leak around filter system. Refitted filters with original tubing then okay.
5. Core Chem - no NO₂ and NO_x above FL150. Also, CO levels went sky high during final profile (background counts to 80ppb).

Aircraft

CCN Rack – Intercom box problems

Satcom Calls

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B208:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	Awaiting completion of post flight processing
CVI	No log is ever taken for CVI

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras
3 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Dave Kindred

EU Aircraft Liaison Officer
Observations Based Research
Jupiter Wing J-M-W014
Met Office
FitzRoy Road
Exeter
Ex1 3PB
UK

Tel: +44 (0)1392 88 4285
Fax: +44 (0)1392 88 5681

E-mail: dave.kindred@metoffice.gov.uk

Flight B208 14:22:13
 Heading 354 deg Speed 321 knots Height 25.0kft Press 375mb
 Lat 39°12.0'N Long 7°24.0'W Wind 15 ms-1/ 283 deg
 Temp -24.52C Dewpoint -33.84C
 From 13:54:50 to now

Current values			
STATIC PRESSURE	375.72	mb	
DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-24.52	deg C	
DEW POINT	-33.84	deg C	

B208 Profile 5

Flight B208 16:28:02
 Heading 97 deg Speed 10 knots Height 0.5kft Press 993mb
 Lat 38°0.0'N Long 7°54.0'W Wind 3 ms-1/ 257 deg
 Temp 28.12C Dewpoint 10.93C
 From 15:52:39 to now

Current values			
STATIC PRESSURE	993.78	mb	
DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	28.13	deg C	
DEW POINT	10.93	deg C	

B208 Profile 7